

IPBES VA Chapter 3 - Systematic PCIV (Principles, Criteria, Indicators, Verifiers) review on valuation methods

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Description: This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment Chapter 3. The methodology explained in this report responds to the mandate of Chapter 3 that will assess different valuation methodologies and approaches, including (a) biophysical, social and cultural, economic, health and holistic (including indigenous and local community-based) and (b) approaches for the integration of different types of values. The systematic review presented in this report was conducted by Chapter 3 to assess the current practice in valuation, how methods are applied, which methods are used in nature valuation, what are they applied for, in which context, and how the methodological challenges identified in reviews of methods families are addressed in applied studies. To provide the necessary evidence for Chapters 3 and 4 a Systematic review was performed¹, this review was later used by Chapter 3, in the Systematic PCIV review which is the main source of scientific evidence of the chapter and in Chapter 4².

¹ Valuation Atlas (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6468906>)

² Systematic review on valuation uptake (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4391335>)

Process overview:

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: 'Systematic PCIV (Principles, Criteria, Indicators, Verifiers) review on valuation methods'

Search languages: English

Search engine: Web of Science

Exact search date: 6 May 2020

Sample extracted: 79 040 papers

Search terms: See (R1) for the extended search terms (VA_3.1 PCIV search terms (R1)). The period of publication used for the search was set from January 1981 - March 2020.

In general, the logic behind keyword selection was that papers should be:

- i) about nature or biodiversity,
- ii) should be an application of valuation methods/approaches,
- iii) should focus on at least one of the value dimensions that we work with in the assessment,
- iv) has the purpose to support decision-making (understood in a broad sense).

To be selected for review a paper had to include a combination of search terms in the NATURE & BIODIVERSITY lists, the VALUE list, DECISION-MAKING PURPOSE list, and the METHODS list in the titles, key words or abstracts of the paper.

Fields extracted:

- Authors (AU)
- Title (TI)
- Journal (SO)
- ISO Source abbreviation (JI)
- Abstract (AB)
- Author keywords (DE)
- Keywords Plus® (ID)
- Language (LA)
- Document Type (DT)
- Web of Science core collection times cited count (TC)
- Author address (C1)
- Digital Object Identifier (DI)
- Publisher Address (PA)
- Article number (AR)
- Editors (BE)
- Funding (FU)
- Publisher (PU)
- Funding text (FX)
- International standard book number (ISBN) (BN)
- International standard serial number (ISSN) (SN)
- Part number (PN)
- Pages (PP)

- Volume (VL)
- Year Published (PY)
- Accession number (UT)
- Cited reference count (NR)
- Research areas (SC)
- Usage count (since 2013) (U2)
- Web of Science categories (WC)
- E-mail Address (EM)
- Book series title (SE)
- Document delivery number (GA)
- Book title (BO)
- Reprint address (RP)
- Database (DB)
- Cited references (CR)

Location and format of the data (A): IPBES_VA 3.1

Corpus_06May20_GEONames_TS_16June20 (A).csv

Treatment applied: (R2) Geographical names extraction. The country names were extracted from fields TI, AB, DE, ID, CI, FU, FX in document (A). They were grouped as (TI, AB, DE, ID) and (CI,FU,FX). Then, they were added to the same document with their ISO 3 codes (<https://www.iso.org/iso-3166-country-codes.html>) as fields:

CountryName_TI_AB_DE_ID

CountryName_CI_FU_FX CI & FU & FX

Treatment applied (R2): IPBES regions and subregions. The country names were later merged by IPBES regions and subregions. IPBES regions and subregions obtained from <https://zenodo.org/record/3928281> These were added to document (A) in fields:

Region_TI_AB_DE_ID

Region_CI_FU_FX

Subregion_TI_AB_DE_ID

Subregion_CI_FU_FX

Sample extracted: 48 781 papers

Treatment applied (R3): Selection of papers based on the mention of the use of methods.

Sample extracted: 33 248 papers.

Treatment applied (R4): Stratified sampling of the papers. Papers were selected to obtain a representative sample of the four regions presented in the IPBES regional assessments, and the four Method Families.

Sample extracted: 3 128 papers.

Treatment applied (R5): Expert screening. Abstracts and titles were screened out when assumptions, claims, or theoretical discussions were made.

Sample extracted: 1 634 papers.

Location and format of the data (B): IPBES_VA_3.1_selected papers 92420 (B).csv

Analysis of the data: 17 reviewers (contributing authors, and TSU support) were recruited to review all the papers. To prepare the reviewers, a virtual workshop took place in April 2020, and a Guidance Manual (R6) was shared with them to help them codify the papers according to 8 different topics: 1) Methods and their use, 2) Context of application, 3) Application descriptors, 4) Reliability and Validity, 5) IPLC, 6) Human well-being, 7) Ecological sustainability, 8) Justice. The emergent data was collected using Google forms (see R7 and R8). Each paper was reviewed at full extent and those that were out of scope were also excluded from the review.

Treatment applied (R9): Papers reviewed at full extent.

Sample extracted: 1 083 papers/ 1 163 applications (included in quantitative/ qualitative/ other synthesis).

Analysis of the data: The 1 163 applications were analyzed and used across Chapter 3 to present the evidence.

Documents attached:

ID	Name	File type	Size	Description
A	IPBES_VA 3.1 Corpus_06May20_GEONames_TS _16June20 (A)	.csv	326.3 MB	CORPUS database with 79 040 papers obtained in the Systematic search in Web of Science.
R1	VA_3.1 PCIV search terms (R1)	.pdf	122 KB	Search terms used to obtain the CORPUS
R1	VA_3.1 PCIV search terms (R1)	.wos	139 KB	Search terms used to obtain the CORPUS in wos format
B	IPBES_VA_3.1_selected papers 92420 (B)	.csv	2.1 MB	Selected papers after expert screening (1 364 papers)
R6	IPBES_VA_3.1 Guidance Manual (R6)	.pdf	705 KB	Guidance manual used by the expert team of contributing authors to review the papers.
R7	IPBES_VA_3.1_STEP 2 - paper screening (R7)	.pdf	252 KB	.pdf version of the google form used to compile the data retrieved from the review. Step 2 compiles the basic information of the paper, screens out papers out of scope.
R8	IPBES_VA_3.1_STEP 3 - Application survey (R8)	.pdf	853 KB	.pdf version of the google form used to compile the data retrieved from the review, according to the 8 different topics mentioned in the

				Guidance Manual.
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